

WATER ABSORPTION BEHAVIOR OF PULTRUDED KENAF FIBER REINFORCED UNSATURATED POLYESTER COMPOSITES AND ITS EFFECTS ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

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SUMMARY

Degradation behavior of kenaf fiber reinforced composites upon exposure to environmental conditions is an important issue. Immersion of composites into various environments is an effective way to investigate the moisture absorption behavior. Effect of water absorption on mechanical properties of composite is of interest to outdoor applications of composites.

Keywords: Kenaf fiber reinforced polyester (KFRUP) composite; Natural fiber reinforced composite (NFRC); Immersion test; Water absorption; Pultrusion process;

ABSTRACT

In this paper, water absorption behavior of pultruded kenaf fiber reinforced unsaturated polyester composites was investigated. Residual compressive properties of the composites after immersion were also reported. Composites were prepared using pultrusion method with minimum kenaf fiber content of 70% w/w. Water absorption tests were performed at room temperature under three different solutions, i.e. distilled water, sea water and acidic solution. The diffusion coefficient of water absorption (D) and maximum moisture content (M_m) were calculated by measuring water uptake of specimen at regular time interval. Highest (M_m) value was recorded for composite immersed in acidic solution followed by sea water and distilled water. While the highest value of diffusion coefficient (D) is sea water followed by acidic solution and distilled water. The water absorption of kenaf fiber reinforced unsaturated polyester composites was found to follow a pseudo Fickian behavior where it did not reach equilibrium. The compressive properties were found to decrease with the increase in the percentage of water uptake. The decay in compression properties were explained by the plasticization of the fiber-matrix interface and swelling of the kenaf fiber.

INTRODUCTION

Natural fibers form an alternative for most widely applied synthetic fiber in composites technology. The interest in natural fiber was known because it is cheap and lighter which provides better stiffness per weight than glass. Natural fiber source is renewable where it considered being green and environmental friendly. The fact that it causes less impact on the environment were proven since natural fiber can be recycled thermally and came from renewable source. By their fairly good mechanical properties the usage of this natural fiber are retained in all sorts of applications. The natural fiber that was used in this study is Kenaf fiber. Kenaf fiber is obtained from stems of plants genus *Hibiscus*, family of *Malvaceae* and the species of *H.cannibinus*. [1] It requires less water to grow because it has growing cycle of 150 to 180 days with average yield of 1700kg/ha. [1]

One of the obstacle in using natural fiber lies on manufacturing technology. If NFRC were to offer an alternative fiber to composite industry, it has to accommodate all the processing avenues of its counterpart, glass fiber. Pultrusion is a unique processing technique for composite manufacturing. Pultruded composite is always associated with high strength, stiffness and particularly due to high fiber content, i.e. 70%. So, there is no other processing technique that could process composite with such fiber content.

The pultrusion process is a continuous molding process to manufacture a composite by using fiber kenaf in thermosetting resin matrix. Reinforced material continuously consolidated into solid composite. The impregnation is accomplished by guiding the reinforcement over and under rods located below the resin surface. [3] When the fiber is dipped into impregnated bath and emerges, it requires shape guidance before being heated in die. Then it is left to cool off before being pulled and cut into the required length.

The thermoset resin impregnates kenaf fiber by filling the layer of continuous fibers on polyester resin in relevant interaction of time/temperature and viscosity. This will affect solvent shrinkage and volatilization on polyester resin when wetting together with kenaf fiber. Then actions that should be handled with care are about continuity and dispersed in good condition of the embedded fibers against excessive stresses between fibers and matrix. [2] The pultrusion machine part system itself shows that it can manufacture the kenaf fiber reinforced polyester composites in good condition.

As we know, our surrounding area is full of moisture and air. All types of polymer composites will absorb moisture when immersed in water or in humid environment. [13] Not only polymer composites, the natural fiber composites are also able to absorb moisture. It is because of the hydrophilic nature of the fiber that is sensitive towards water absorption, causing instability in the properties. [5] There are three different mechanisms that conduct the moisture penetration into composites materials namely: (1) diffusion of water molecules into the micro gaps between polymer chains, which is the main mechanism, (2) capillary transport into the gaps and flaws at the interfaces between fibers and polymer, due to incomplete wettability and impregnation, and (3) transport by micro cracks in the matrix, formed during the

compounding process [5]. Then the water immersion test was done in order to evaluate the effects of water absorption on its mechanical properties or the kenaf fiber reinforced polyester composites.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

Kenaf fiber was obtained from herbaceous annual plant extracted from stem provided by Malaysian Kenaf and Tobacco Board (LTN). The polyester resin used for the study was purchased from Revetex Company.

Preparations of composites

Unidirectional Kenaf fiber reinforced unsaturated polyester composites were prepared using pultrusion technique. It was manufactured in MMG Composites Sdn. Bhd. The kenaf fiber is stored in a creel stand, and is then guided into preheating chamber. Then pulled it through the heated die where the kenaf fiber fully impregnated with polymer matrix before going into cooling die. Pulling device at the end of the pultrusion machine is to pull the unidirectional kenaf fiber material composites through the die of the pultrusion line. The parameters of pulling speed and heating die temperature used for the processed is given in tables 1.

Table 1 Parameter of the pultrusion

Parameter	Pulling speed (mm/min)	Temperature (°C)
Kenaf fibre pultruded composites	195 – 210	135

Material characterization

Water absorption tests

Moisture uptake was determined by measuring the weight periodically by soaking the specimen in water. The specimens were obtained by cutting according ASTM D5229. The specimens for compression test were cut into 25.4 mm length and 12.7 mm diameter cylinder. Prior to absorption experiments, the samples were dried until the weight stabilized. The specimens were then immersed in distilled water, sea water and acidic solution at room temperature and the weight change monitored as a function of time. The absorption behavior weighed at 24, 48, 72, 96, and 120 up to 504 hour within 5min of removing from the liquid water, was studied.

Mechanical properties

Compression test

Compression test were done at room temperature in accordance to ASTM D695 [6] test method with a diameter 12.7mm and 25.4mm in length. The crosshead speed was

5 mm/min. The standard determines the behavior of materials deformation at various loads was recorded when the loads compress.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Water absorption

Water absorption behavior of the composite is a concern in composites structural applications. The water absorption property depends on the percentage content of the fiber, fiber orientation, temperature, area of the exposed surface, permeability of fibers, void content, hydrophilicity of the individual components etc [13]. Figure 1 shows the moisture content of composites for composites and flexural specimen in distilled water, sea water and acidic solution. Weight gain rate (%) was calculated by

$$M\% = \frac{M_t - M_0}{M_0} \cdot 100 \quad (1)$$

Where M (%) is the moisture content in percentage; M_t is the weight of the wet sample at the Time t ; and M_0 is the initial weight of the sample.

From the figure it shows that the moisture content increased with time. When specimens were immersed, the water molecules penetrate and inducing the weight gain. At the beginning of the curve, the weight increased sharply demonstrating the rapid moisture penetration into the composite materials. The curves in Fig. 1 of compression specimen immersed in distilled water is in two stages diffusion process where it shows an increasing trend at first and followed by decreasing trend, while the one immersed in sea water shows an abrupt jump and continue to increase gradually. In acidic solution, the curve is in two stages diffusion but still following an increasing trend.

Fig. 1 Water absorption content curves in distilled water, sea water and acidic solution for compression specimens.

After 21 days sea water treatment for compression specimen, the surface turned black and pink particles oozed out from the specimens. This might be due to the extraction of soluble materials which may cause a loss in weight of the specimen [8, 9, and 10]. The weights gain may be due to the absorption and extraction of soluble compound [8]. In distilled water and acidic solution white particles oozed out from the composites specimen and the reaction was the same as described.

Table 2 summarises the diffusion coefficient, D and maximum of the moisture content for flexural and compression sample in three conditions. The diffusion coefficient or diffusivity has the dimensions of [length² time⁻¹], [m² s⁻¹] and is calculated from the slope of moisture content to square root of time by Eq. (2). The slopes were taken at linearly early stage of absorption process. Diffusion coefficients for compression specimen among the three conditions, the diffusion coefficient in sea water condition are higher than acidic solution and distilled water. The maximum moisture content, M_m shows that compression specimen immersed in acidic solution is the highest compared to other conditions.

$$D = \pi \left(\frac{h}{4M_m} \right)^2 \left(\frac{M_t - M_e}{\sqrt{t_2} - \sqrt{t_1}} \right)^2 \quad (2)$$

Table 2 The diffusion coefficient and maximum moisture content of kenaf fiber reinforced polyester composites in flexural and compression sample.

Parameters	Conditions		
	Distilled Water	Sea Water	Acidic Solution
D x 10 ⁻⁴ (m ² /s)	3.16	3.42	3.20
M _m (%)	16.41	20.67	23.33

Compression test

In general, the composite specimens under compression fail by shear crippling or kinking [11 and 12]. The matrix/fiber interface may fracture in shear where fiber buckles lead to an ultimate failure [11]. Fig. 2 shows the variation of stress-strain diagram of specimen immersed in the distilled water, sea water and acidic solution. All the curves in the three different conditions of immersion were below standard curve. It can be seen that the acidic solution curve is almost a straight line and there is an abrupt end to the curve. This indicates that the composite specimen shows a non elastic materials behavior after immersion. The curves representing sea water and distilled water are also non elastic in behavior but with a little warning once their limits are surpassed. In Fig. 3, 4 and 5, the compression strength, maximum compression strain at failure and modulus values of the different immersion conditions are plotted. First, we can observe similar decreasing trend

of compression strength and modulus while the compression strain failures are increasing in all the three conditions.

Fig. 2 Summary of flexural stress-strain curve of KFRUP under various conditions.

Fig. 3 Compression strength versus environmental condition.

Fig. 4 Maximum compression strain at break/failure versus environmental condition

Fig. 5 Compression modulus versus environmental condition.

The entire trend of the samples after immersion is decreasing compared to standard sample that was not being immersed (standard). It is because of the moisture content interface between matrix and fiber where the formation of hydrogen bonding between the water molecules and cellulose fiber are the cause for the mechanical properties to decrease as moisture contents increase [13]. The kenaf fiber are hydrophilic with many hydroxyl groups (-OH) in the fiber structure forming a large number of hydrogen bonds between the macromolecules of the cellulose and polyester matrix [13 and 14]

CONCLUSIONS

Kenaf fiber reinforced composites were successfully prepared using pultrusion process. Rod specimen with approximately 70% of kenaf content water absorption study had revealed that the water diffusion in the pultruded kenaf fiber reinforced polyester composites in sea water are higher than acidic solution and distilled water. The rates of moisture uptake increased with immersion time and were non-Fickian. The moisture content of the hydrophilic kenaf fiber may cause compatibility exhibited between the hydrophobic polyester polymeric matrix. In short, the kenaf fiber can be used as a potential reinforced in polyester resin. And also pultrusion process is a better technique to fabricate kenaf fiber reinforced composites with good properties.

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